

FHERITALE

STAKEHOLDER MEETING

Cross-sector synergies among RIs to strengthen European research on the impact of micro- and nanoplastics

THE EVENT

The FHERITALE Stakeholder Event, held in Brussels on 26 May 2026, brought together representatives of European Research Infrastructures (RIs), academia, industry, regulatory organisations and European initiatives to discuss current challenges and future priorities related to micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) and other artificial materials. The event aimed to strengthen dialogue across the Food–Health–Environment domains and gather stakeholder input to support future service development, infrastructure coordination and strategic roadmapping activities.

The core outcomes emerged from two co-creation sessions: these activities enabled participants to identify major research challenges, discuss systemic barriers and collectively explore possible solutions. Specifically, the discussions revealed strong convergence around the need for harmonised methodologies, validated reference materials, improved metrological capabilities, better access to RIs, interoperable data ecosystems and enhanced training opportunities. At the same time, stakeholders emphasised that scientific progress alone will not be sufficient to address the challenges associated with micro- and nanoplastics. Prevention, mitigation, sustainable innovation and stronger interactions between science and policy were identified as equally important priorities. In this framework, RIs are viewed not only as providers of analytical services but also as facilitators of collaboration and integration across disciplines and sectors.

PROGRAM

Morning: Vision & Strategic Landscape

High-level institutional opening, keynote lecture, and an interactive roundtable exploring the current state of the art and key gaps in the research infrastructure landscape.

PANELIST TABLE MORNING SESSION

Marja Lamoree
(Vrije Universiteit
Amsterdam)

Veronica Maria Teresa
Lattanzio
(EU Food Safety Platform)

Ana Portugal Melo
(MIRRI-ERIC)

Andrea Valsesia
(JRC)

Moderator: Claudia Zoani (ENEA)

Strategic roundtables focused on challenges and the co-creation of policy and scientific recommendations, contributing to future FHERITALE outputs.

Afternoon: Dialogue with Stakeholders & Policymakers

PANELIST TABLE AFTERNOON SESSION

Johanna Bischof
(Euro-BioImaging)

Jessica Catalano
(CSIL)

Katherine Santizo
(CEFIC)

Dimosthenis
Sarigiannis
(NHRF)

Catherine
Simoneau
(JRC)

Moderator: Michele Suman (Barilla)

MICRO- AND NANOPLASTIC RESEARCH: CURRENT STATE & FUTURE NEEDS

Keynote by Tanja Ćirković Veličković
University of Belgrade

ANALYTICAL METHODS

- ILCs (Inter-Laboratory Comparisons) for improved harmonization.
- Particle sizing (1–200 μm by LD; 50–400 nm by DLS) \rightarrow good consistency.
- Detection: μ -FTIR, μ -Raman, LDIR, Py-GC/MS, TED-GC/MS \rightarrow good identification, quantification remains challenging.

Research on MNPs is advancing rapidly across EU, with strong efforts to understand Human exposure, Toxicological assessment and Hazard identification and develop robust methods to detect them.

The keynote lecture by Tanja Ćirković Veličković comprehensively reviewed the MNPs research landscape, detailing recent progress alongside critical knowledge gaps. Despite scientific advances, significant hurdles remain. The research pipeline is constrained by detection limitations, characterisation complexities, a lack of reference materials, and poor analytical comparability. Overcoming these requires an immediate focus on harmonised methodologies, international standardisation, and unified research strategies. To this end, recent European initiatives are playing a pivotal role. Through coordinated roadmaps and shared frameworks, they are successfully aligning scientific evidence with stakeholder needs to build a unified response to the MNPs issue.

EU initiatives

Stakeholder input

Harmonisation and Standardisation

One of the strongest and most consistent messages emerging from this interactive session was the need for harmonised methodologies and standardised analytical procedures. Participants highlighted that the current research landscape remains fragmented, with different laboratories relying on different protocols, sample preparation procedures, analytical techniques, and reporting formats. This fragmentation limits the comparability of results across studies and reduces confidence in the evidence generated. Importantly, standardisation was not framed as a purely technical issue. Rather, it was recognised as a fundamental prerequisite for scientific credibility, regulatory acceptance, data interoperability, and long-term progress in the field.

Reference Materials and Metrology

The availability of reference materials emerged as one of the highest priorities identified during the session. Participants stressed that reliable measurements depend on the availability of validated materials to support calibration, method development, and quality assurance. However, developing environmentally realistic reference materials remains highly challenging, as they must accurately reflect the complexity of real-world matrices and degradation processes. As a result, this was recognised not only as a scientific challenge but also as a significant investment priority. Closely linked to this discussion was the importance of metrology, which participants viewed as a strategic foundation for generating reliable data and supporting downstream activities such as exposure assessment, risk assessment, and policymaking.

Access to Research Infrastructures

Europe possesses world-leading facilities and expertise. Nevertheless, many participants identified barriers related to cost, limited awareness of available services, administrative complexity, and the specialised nature of advanced technologies. Several contributions suggested that a challenge is not necessarily the lack of technologies, but rather the difficulty of accessing and effectively using existing capabilities. This observation is consistent with the familiarity of the participants with RIs.

VISION & STRATEGIC LANDSCAPE: HIGH-LEVEL ROUND TABLE

MAIN LIMITING PROGRESS GAP

Which gap most limits your work or application today?

The feedback highlights that the absence of standardized protocols is considered the single largest obstacle to research, with over half of the respondents identifying it as the primary bottleneck.

RISKS OF UNADDRESSED GAPS

Limited regulatory update

Poor data compatibility

Reduced impact of research

ONE ACTION FOR THE BIGGEST DIFFERENCE

Data integration and harmonisation emerged as the main drivers of progress in MNPs research.

IMPACT & POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS: STRATEGIC ROUNDTABLE

The afternoon programme, moderated by Michele Suman, moved from problem identification towards solution-oriented discussions. Participants were assigned six different challenges:

1. Reference materials
2. Enhance technology development
3. Research gaps
4. Realistic scenarios
5. Mitigation strategies
6. Training needs

The transition from the morning to the afternoon was particularly significant. While the first session focused primarily on identifying barriers, this last part encouraged participants to reflect on practical actions and future priorities.

IMPACT & POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS: STRATEGIC ROUNDTABLE

REFERENCE MATERIALS

1

Plastics are complex and to understand exposure and potential effects what kind and how many test materials (standards and reference) are needed to ensure replicable results and outcomes for risk assessment.

Start from materials that we can reproducibly produce and include matrices. Development of references is very expensive so investment on metrology is needed.

2

Coordinate research infrastructures to deliver joint services, bridge the gap between developers and researchers to meet priority needs, and promote awareness and regulatory acceptance of new technologies.

Need of pilots involving technology developers, research labs, regulatory authorities, industrial associations.

ENHANCE TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT

REALISTIC SCENARIOS

TRAINING

RESEARCH GAPS

3

Current approaches do not provide a full understanding of MNPs-organism/environment interactions, underscoring the need for improved and novel methodologies.

Consider tried and tested epidemiological studies using MNPs to get initial data. Characterisation of MNPs in several environments to understand their prevalence. Prioritisation.

4

How can lab experiments support validation of models and ensure realistic scenarios (i.e., matching what is found in environment) are addressed for predictions of micro- and nano-plastic concentrations.

1. How do plastics degrade under different conditions? More funds are needed for mechanistic insights.
2. What are relevant point exposure scenarios, validated in laboratory conditions?

MITIGATION STRATEGIES

5

Reduce the release of nanoplastics into the environment, including improved waste management and product design, including the role of alternatives materials (e.g., bioplastics).

Analysis of the alternatives with its respective impacts, social and economical feasibility, and the transparency needed to come to the different approaches and agreed constraints.

6

Significant need for training on the proper use of analytical methods and the interpretation of data, as well as on the definition of artificial materials and their impact within the One-Health framework; training on how to proper coordinate RIs to address specific challenges/needs.

RIs can provide training for advanced technologies, but how to translate this for non experts from other disciplines? Training on ONE-HEALTH concept, trade-off and cost/benefits?

In the scheme above, the text of each challenge is shown along with a brief outcome of the discussion (white boxes)

IDENTIFIED ENABLING FACTORS

The outcomes of the interactive afternoon session highlighted several strategic priorities for advancing research on micro- and nanoplastics beyond current analytical approaches. Rather than representing isolated research needs, these priorities converged into six key enabling factors: the fundamental conditions required to strengthen scientific excellence, foster collaboration and accelerate the translation of research into policy and societal impact.

Participants stressed that scientific evidence on MNPs must be underpinned by robust **Method Validation**, achieved through independent verification, inter-laboratory comparison exercises and quality assurance mechanisms to ensure the reliability of analytical data. This, in turn, relies on **Metrology & Quality** as harmonised measurement approaches enabling analytical results to be accurate, reproducible and comparable across laboratories. At the same time, effective **Coordination** among RIs, European projects, industry and regulatory bodies was recognised as essential for integrating expertise, avoiding fragmentation and building a trusted scientific ecosystem.

The discussions also highlighted the need to move beyond contamination monitoring towards research that actively supports mitigation strategies. Achieving this objective requires the adoption of **Real Scenarios**, promoting environmentally relevant materials and realistic exposure conditions that incorporate ageing and degradation processes.

IDENTIFIED ENABLING FACTORS

Participants further encouraged interdisciplinary approaches, recognising that knowledge from fields such as heritage and conservation sciences could provide valuable insights into long-term material degradation and improve the environmental relevance of experimental studies.

Finally, **Training** emerged as a strategic enabler for developing the next generation of researchers. Participants emphasised that addressing the complexity of MNPs requires interdisciplinary competencies and closer collaboration across scientific communities, resulting in a more effective research and evidence-based decision making. The latter should take into account the **Social Dimension** of actions. In particular, the participants observed that policies designed to influence consumer behaviour may generate uneven impacts across different social groups, ultimately impacting affordability, fairness and public acceptance.

CONCLUSION

The Brussels stakeholder event provided valuable insights into the priorities, concerns and expectations of communities involved in MNPs research. The discussions revealed that many of the barriers currently limiting progress are not purely technological. Rather, they reflect broader challenges related to harmonisation, validation, accessibility, interoperability, training and coordination across the European research landscape.

The interactive sessions highlighted a strong convergence among stakeholders regarding current challenges in the field as well as the actions needed to address them. Participants consistently emphasised the importance of standardisation, metrology, RI access, realistic exposure scenarios, understanding biological interactions, and interdisciplinary capacity building. The event highlighted a growing perception that RIs should play a broader role than simply providing analytical services by guiding technological innovation.

This strategic meeting provided important guidance for the future activities of FHERITALE and reinforced the strategic relevance of coordinated RIs ecosystems in addressing the complex challenges associated with MNPs research in Europe.

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